

Towards Enabling School Career Services Delivery in Tanzania: The Role of Students, Teacher Counselors and Heads of Schools.

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Abstract: School career service delivery refers to establishment, provision and engagement of students in career activities by school career counselors for the purpose of helping them to obtain skills necessary for making informed career decision during and after school journey. Since the counseling service is a voluntary activity, it is necessary for students and teacher counselors to willingly participate in this exercise so as to make career services' delivery effective. This paper intended to identify students' knowledge with career services available in schools, students' frequency of participation in career activities at school, students' attitude towards career services offered in schools and students' awareness on various career options. The paper also examined teachers' perception towards career services delivery by comparing government and international schools. The sample for the study included six secondary schools with a total number of 322 students, 6 heads of schools and 6 teacher counselors. Information from students were collected through questionnaire and focus group discussion while the interview was used for teacher counselors and heads of schools. The *t*-test shows a significant difference in scores for government school students ($M=28.88, SD=6.76$) as compared to international school students [$M=41.37, SD=11.67; t(194) = -11.03, p=.000$], also students' frequency of participation in career activities was good among international school students as compared to students in government school. Apart from that international school students expressed positive attitude ($M=39.47, SD=3.82$) towards career services delivery in schools as compared to low attitude from government school students ($M=29.77, SD=2.58$). In line to that, many international school students expressed good awareness in various career options as compared to students in government schools. On the other hand, teachers in international schools perceived career services delivery to be very important as compared to low consideration expressed by teachers from government schools. It was therefore concluded that, career services delivery in international schools is to some degrees' effective as compared to government schools. It is therefore recommended that, awareness seminars and workshops are necessary especially in government schools in order to make career services provision effective. In line to that, future research can focus on the relevance of the current career counselors' training in preparing teacher counselors to work in schools in Tanzania.

Key words: Career services delivery, Attitude, Perception.

Introduction

Although there are many career opportunities in the world of work such as teaching, accounting, engineering, social work and medicine, many people often face difficulties in career decision making (Biswalo, 1996).

Kidd (2006) in his recommendations about successful career decision making argue that, careers emerge to individuals through the interaction between an individual agency and the experience, constraining and enabling forces of the social context. Hence from this fact it can be emphasized that people's experience of careers over their life courses reflect their changing needs, values, aspiration and attitudes towards work. Belkin (1981) add that, the only way to help individuals to decide upon educational plans, make appropriate career choices and succeed in all educational endeavors is through making career orientation and career knowledge provision a realistic practice. Therefore, facts pointed out by these scholars calls for serious career counseling delivery to individuals especially the growing youth and adolescents in schools with a focus of providing career knowledge and career adjustment skills among school leavers.

The Problem and its Context

The departure of colonial administration influenced the need for East African countries to ensure availability of skilled labour in their countries. Having the same intention, the government of Tanzania increased the number of schools and enrolment in order to meet the labour market, a process which went hand in hand with establishment and restructuring of

career paths named subject combinations (Maduki, 1993; Psacharopoulos and Loxley; 1985, Malekela, 1983; and Omari, 1977). Malekela (1983) explains further that, despite the expansion of school opportunities and restructuring subject combinations, the performance and students' ability for career decision making was poor, the situation which affected their recruitment both in the government and private sectors. In fact the inadequacy in career decision making skills among students were linked to the lack of career information, inadequate career knowledge and ineffective career services delivery in schools.

Following the discovered weaknesses in career decision making among school leavers in the country, the government decided to introduce career services provision as an integral part of the country's education system by instructing heads of secondary schools to appoint school career counselors. The counselors were required to advise heads of schools in matters related to applications for careers and training for students, assisting students with occupational information and their requirements. Furthermore, career counselors were required to help students in making long range plans of study so that they can apply to educational institutions where they can receive advanced training before joining the world of work (MOEC-Kiongozi cha Mkuu wa Shule, 1997, Page.20).

The good intention from the government in line to career counseling services provision in schools is not currently

realistic. This is due to lack of effective career programmes and career facilities to help the appointed career counselors to manage their duties (Nkuba, 2010). The situation is worse in government schools as opposed to international schools where career services provision is to some degree a reality (Nkuba, 2012).

Literature review

Knowledge as Determinants for participation in Career Activities

Biswalo (1996), Ndambuki and Mutie (1999) emphasize that occupational information in terms of valid and usable data about different career options, positions, duties, entrance requirements, conditions of work, rewards offered, and advancement patterns are very crucial in career decision making. Explaining the importance of career knowledge and information, Parsons in his trait and factor theory as cited in Sharf (1992) explains that, to select a career, an individual should ideally have; first information which indicates a clear understanding of himself/herself, his/her attitudes, abilities, interests, ambitions, resources, limitations, and their causes. Second an individual should have knowledge of the requirements and conditions for success, advantages and disadvantages, compensation, opportunities and prospects in different lines of work. Moreover an individual should have a true reasoning on the relations of himself/herself and the requirements of success (Parsons, 1909, p. 5) as cited in Sharf, 1992). In fact, the trait and factor theory holds that individuals need to understand their abilities, aptitudes, interests and skills (traits) and match these to the specific requirements and demands (factors). Apart from that successful matching of individual traits with job factors is the key to a successful and satisfying career decision a situation which can be attained by having adequate career knowledge. With arguments from these scholars, it is true to the fact that the inadequacy in terms of career knowledge is more likely to affect the individuals in career activities due to unclear need and necessity and benefits which the intended individual can get from the service.

Listing the major points which influence career choice, Hoppock, as cited in Belkin (1981) explains that, vocational development begins when we first become aware that an occupation can help to meet our needs. Vocational development progresses and occupational choices improves as we become better able to anticipate how well a prospective occupation will meet our needs. Thus our capacity to anticipate depends upon our knowledge of ourselves, our knowledge of occupations and our ability to think clearly. Hoppock adds that information about ourselves affects occupational choice by helping us to recognize what we want and by helping us to anticipate whether or not we will be successful in collecting what the contemplated occupation offer to us. For these reasons, information about occupations affects occupational choices by helping us to discover the occupations that may meet our needs and by helping us to anticipate how well satisfied we may hope to be in one

occupation as compared with another. Therefore career knowledge is necessary so as to help students in identifying their weaknesses as well as the job requirements the need which can attract them to participate in career activities for the purpose of addressing their weaknesses and matching their personal characteristics with career options exposed to them in career activities conducted in schools.

Attitude as a predictor for Engagement in Career Services

Intentions to perform a given behaviour can be predicted from attitudes towards the behaviour or behavioral process (Ajzen, 1991). It should be noted that attitudes, like other hypothetical constructs are not directly observable or measurable, their existence is inferred from a certain class of evaluative responses to the attitude object. Evaluating responses of behavioral type consists of the overt actions that people exhibit in relation to the attitude object (Ajzen, 1991). Therefore students' evaluation of career services delivery in schools can be useful in suggesting their intention to participate and engaging in the available career services.

It has been further argued that people who evaluate an attitude object favourably tend to engage in behaviours that foster or support it, and people who evaluate an attitude object unfavourably tend to engage in behaviours that hinder or oppose it (Henerson, 1987). Therefore it is true to the fact that, positive attitudes for students towards career services offered in schools can have implication on their participation and use of the information obtained in different career activities while the opposite is true if there is negative attitude among students.

Explaining the importance of attitude in career decision making in his theory of planned behaviour, Ajzen (1988; 1991) points out that, the most determinant of behaviour performance is the intention to engage in that behaviour. Thus the theory of planned behaviour suggests that, the link between intention and behaviour reflect the fact that people tend to engage by practice in behaviours they intend to perform. In fact Ajzen describes the necessity of information in the process of career decision making basing on various dimensions which generally place emphasis on attitude of an individual.

Moreover, a longitudinal study done by Kolvereid and Isaksen (2005) among 297 Norwegians, also reported attitude to have a significant moderate correlation with an individual's intention for self-employment $r = .39, p < .05$. These facts explain that, with positive attitude towards any activity, individuals tend to have intention for participating.

That is why, the focus in this paper is to examine students attitudes towards career services offered in schools so as it can be used to predict the participation of students in these services which is available to help them in improving their career decision making skills.

Perception and its Implication in Career Services Delivery

Zanden (1987) explains that, perception is the mediating link between individuals and their environment. It is the ability to derive information from the environment, interpret the information, and act upon. Therefore in consideration to the explained facts, teachers in schools are in position to derive information and interpret them in consideration to their observations and evaluation of career services delivery taking place in schools.

This interpretation might predict their reaction towards career services delivery in schools which are necessary in examining their support in the provision.

Snyder and Uranowitz as cited in Zanden (1987) emphasize also that, “We live our lives not in isolation, but in social world. Consequently we must gather and interpret information about objects, events, and other phenomenon in our environment. The process of interpreting the elements and events in our environment helps us to know the characteristics, qualities and inner state of the environment. This process helps us to predict about the future action which might occur in our context”. Therefore teachers’ perception has great impact on their participation in assisting students so as they can participate and gain the necessary career choice skills in their educational journey.

Rao (2008) emphasize that, perception is a process by which individuals organize and interpret their sensory perceives in order to give meaning to their environment. However, what one perceives can be substantially different from objective reality. There need be, but there is often, disagreement. In perception process an individual selects, organizes, and interprets information inputs to create a meaningful picture of the world. Perception depends not only on the physical stimuli, but also on the stimuli’s relation to the surrounding field and on conditions within the individual. Therefore, with Rao argument it can be suggested that, environment with which and individual is found can affect his or her perception, meaning that environmental factors which relate with career services delivery exercise can affect the individuals comment on the exercise. Generally career services delivery in government and international schools can be influenced by different factors which vary from one type of school to another. Such factors can affect the teacher counselors and heads of schools interpretation and comments on this service.

Statement of the Problem

Career decision making among youth and school students in Tanzania have been a challenge since independence, this situation was linked to the lack of career information, inadequate career knowledge as well as poor career decision making skills among individuals in the country (Malekela, 1983). As a response to the inadequate career decision making skills among school students, the government of Tanzania through the then Ministry of Education and Culture introduced career services provision in secondary schools for the purpose of addressing the challenges related to inadequate career decision making skills among students (MOEC, 1997). It is

due to this fact the current paper seeks to examine the role of students, teacher counselors and heads of schools in the success of the existing career services delivery in secondary schools by comparing the level of success or failure in the two context and reasons for the same.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the objectives of the study were;

- To examine students’ level of participation in various career services provided in selected government and international schools.
- To examine students’ attitude towards career services delivery in selected government and international schools.
- To assess students’ career knowledge in selected government and international schools
- To examine teacher counselors and heads of schools’ perception towards career services delivery in schools.

Basic Research Questions of the Study

- What are students’ level of participation in various career services provided in selected government and international schools?
- What is students’ attitude towards career services delivery in selected government and international schools?
- What is students’ career knowledge in selected government and international schools
- What are teacher counselors and heads of schools’ perception towards career services delivery in schools?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed both quantitative and qualitative research approaches so as to minimize the weaknesses of each. Kombo and Tromp (2006) insist that, quantitative and qualitative approaches to research are complimentary, they should be used together so as to maximize the strength and minimize the limitations of each. With quantitative approach, the cross sectional survey research design was used, this was considered to suffice the study demands because it allows collection of data from secondary schools with different characteristics. Bryman (2004), Gay, Mills, & Airrasian (2006) emphasizes that, cross sectional survey is good design for collecting information in a relatively short period of time and making predictions.

The study was conducted in Dar es Salaam region, Tanzania. The majority of people in this region are engaged in office works in government, international and private institutions. This area was considered to be ideal for this study due to presence of international schools which are oldest in the country. Dar es Salaam being the city has many people facing challenges related to unemployment in the country. The target population for the present study included high school

students. These individuals included international and government school students who were estimated to be 2,000 aged from 17 years and above.

High school students were an interesting subpopulation due to the reasons that they have already defined their career paths

through their subject combination which they are currently taking at this level of study. Apart from that, this is a group of students who are in transition from adolescence to early adulthood where different behaviours including career decision making are engaged, tried and internalized ready for adult normative roles (Lugoe, 1996; Santrock, 2005; MOEC, 1995).

The sample of the present study includes 322 students, 6 teacher counselors and 6 heads of schools as indicated in table 1. The sample size was determined by using sampling error of 5 percent with confidence level of 95 percent (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison's (2000).

Table 1: Number of students and Teachers included in the study

School	Number of students		S/ Heads	C/ counselors	Total
	Females	Males			
<i>Tambaza</i>	38	32	1	1	72
<i>Jangwani</i>	60	-	1	1	62
<i>Azania</i>	-	60	1	1	62
<i>Laureate</i>	34	26	1	1	62
<i>Academic International</i>	20	20	1	1	42
<i>Agakhan mzizima</i>	16	16	1	1	34
<i>Total</i>	168	154	6	6	334

The demographic and descriptive characteristics of the respondents were also considered in sample selection for students to be included in the study as summarized in table 2

Socio-demographic variable	Category	Frequency (%)
Age	17 years	61 (19.0)
	18-19 years	182 (56.5)
	20 years to 21 years old	79 (24.5)
Sex	Females	168 (52.2)
	Males	154 (47.8)
School type	Public	190 (59)
	Private	132 (41)
Subject combinations	Sciences (eg. PCM, PCB, CBN, CBM, PMI, etc.)	113 (35.1)
	Business (eg. ECA, EGM, HGE, etc.)	110 (34.2)
	Arts (eg. HGL, HGK, HKL, etc.)	99 (30.7)
Total		322 (100)

Generally, demographic and descriptive characteristics of students involved in the study suggests that, majority of them were in the early adulthood age where the issue of career choice is apparent (Cobb, 2001; Santrock, 2005). In case of sampling the number differed due to the large number of students registered in government schools as compared to the small number of students in international schools. The use of stratified and simple random sampling was practical in student's selection and the purposeful sampling was used for teacher counselors and heads of schools. For the matter of generalization, results from this study may be shared light across high schools in the country so as to serve as an alert to the area addressed in this paper.

Moreover, the researcher used questionnaires, focus group discussion and interview as methods of data collection. The integration of these methods enabled the study to have adequate quantitative and qualitative data for the triangulation and analysis process (Best & Kahn, 2006; Gay et al., 2006).

Data obtained through questionnaires were coded and total scores by major sections or items representing various clusters were computed. Frequencies computation and determination of descriptive statistics were done through statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 15.0 (Pallat, 2005). Moreover, the qualitative information obtained through focus group discussions and interviews were descriptively analyzed and major summaries were reported together with some direct quotations from respondents in providing more insight on the answers provided by respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students' level of Participation in Various Career Activities/Sources Available in Schools

Table3: Students' level of Participation in Various Career Activities Available in Schools

Career programme available in schools	Response from students	
	Government students (190)	International students (132)
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Career resource books reading	28(14.7)	60(45.5)
Mass media shows and provision	113 (59.5)	77 (58.3)
Internet sources available in schools	11(5.8)	106 (80.3)
Peers discussion and brainstorming	183 (96.3)	94 (71.2)
Personal advice from teachers	161 (84.7)	106 (80.3)
Attending Career speakers talks	23 (12.1)	52 (39.4)
Career visit organized by school	8 (4.2)	105 (79.5)
Participating in Career clubs	1 (0.5)	73 (55.3)
Visiting Career resource banks available in school libraries	62 (32.6)	26 (19.7)
Attending career exhibitions organized at school	1 (0.5)	104 (78.7)
Attending career counseling	1(0.5)	9 (6.8)

Among several career sources and activities which students

These findings can be explained by different factors,

said that they do participate includes peer discussion 183 (96.3%) in government schools and 94 (71.2%) in international schools, personal advice from teachers 161 (84.7%) in government schools and 106 (80.6%) in international schools, mass media 113 (59.5%) in government schools and 77(58.3%) for international schools. It was revealed in this study also that, these are major sources of career information among these students in schools. Furthermore, there were clear differences in the level of participation in various sources and careers activities among international and government schools. The differences are revealed as follows; career exhibition in government schools identified with 01(0.5%) student as compared to 104(78.7%) students in international schools.

The use of career visit 8(4.2%) students in government schools and 105(79.5%) students in international schools, use of internet sources and instructions 11(5.8%) students in government schools and 106(80.3%) students in international schools, career club 01(0.5%) student in government and 73 (55.3%) students for international schools.

some of these factors are such as the difference in level of exposure in career programmes among students in government and international schools and different orientation from teachers in government and international schools. This argument is true because many school managements and teachers in Tanzania especially the ones owned by government have failed to organize and bring in contact the reliable source of career information to students. During the focus group discussions it was revealed that there is much dependence of students to peers for career information than other sources of career knowledge. This is due to fact that, there is inadequate career information, career facilities and trained career teachers from which students can learn about careers so as to reduce confusions in subject choice and career decision making (Biswalo, 1996). During the focus group discussion one student from one of the government secondary schools emphasized that;

I got to know about careers by discussing with our friends in higher classes and in discussion among ourselves. This is because we don't know where and how to get more information to guide our studies so as to match with jobs of our interest. Our teachers have shown less concern in helping us in this area.

Due to explained facts, it is clear that, students especially in government schools are depending more to peers and untrained career teachers as source of career information. This suggests that, if our teachers are not well trained in careers services provision there is danger of having secondary school leavers who cannot explain about who they want to be and from what attribute they think they can become that way.

Similarly students indicated that they have access to different media such as newspapers which in the researchers view they get less benefit in terms of career mentorship. This is due to the fact that, even these newspapers are found in schools, who is guiding students in looking issues which are in line to career and how these information can be used by these students in improving their learning. The research is asking this question

because the teacher counselors found in schools are also ignorance of the same. Hence training for teachers, career facilities and adequate career programmes must be introduced in schools so as to help students to realize their potentials and match them with the world of work.

Arguing in the same line Hill & Nathan (2006) as well as Kidd (2006) acknowledge the role of mass media in providing career information to individuals in various contexts. In line to this observation Ndambuki and Mutie (1999) add that in the Tanzanian context, the common source of career information are parents and relatives, teachers, peers, books and mass media in which the news papers and television programmes has high contribution in youth career decision process.

Therefore, if this is the case the youth are in danger of intering careers by simply coping rather than matching what they can do and the available opportunities in the world of work. This can help them to begin preparation in line to a certain career so as to compete effectively in employment seeking after their school life.

Generally the results from government and international school respondents indicates that international school students are having more career sources and activities which they participate, the situation which is more likely to favour them in their career decision making process as compared to students in government schools. It is the opinion of the researcher that government schools teachers, managers and heads of schools should learn from international schools on how to organise, facilitate and manage career services delivery so as to help students whom many of the are in government schools.

Students' Attitude towards Career Services Available in Schools

In this study, the measurement of students' attitude was done by considering three levels of responses which include the value larger than the median indicating positive attitude, the median which implies undecided or not sure and the value smaller than the median which implies negative attitude. Calculation of the mean score using descriptive statistics was carried out and the results were as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for Students' Attitude towards Available Career Services among Government and International School Students

Type of school	N	Min.	Median	Max.	Mean	SD	T	df	Sig.
Government	190	10	30	50	29.77	2.58	-25.44	212.42	.000
International	132	10	30	50	39.47	3.82			

Mean difference is significant at $p < .05$

In the lickert scale used, the score for government schools students was ($M=29.77$, $SD=2.58$). The results suggests that students' attitude in government schools range fro negative to not sure whether career services offered in their schools are important or not on their career decision making. This is because the mean score value obtained from these schools are very close to the mean which is at lower but approximately close to 30 median measure. However, for international school students, the mean score reveals positive attitude at ($M=39.47$, $SD=3.82$), a mean score value which is larger than the median. This result suggests positive consideration by international school students on the career services provided in their schools. The obtained results reveal a significant difference in attitude for students in government and international schools towards career services delivery. That is to say government school students revealed a mean score close to the median which portray negative to undecided attitude at the score of ($M= 29.77$, $SD=2.58$), different from international school students who showed positive attitude towards career services offered at school at the score of [$M= 37.47$, $SD= 3.82$; $t(212.42) = -25.44$, $p=.000$].

The magnitude of the difference in the mean score between government and international schools students was very large

(*eta squared* .67), which is equal to 67 percent. This difference might be due to low level of career knowledge, awareness and experience in career activities for government school students as compared to international school students. In line to this observation Ajzen (1988) argue that, perceived behavioral control determines the attitude of an individual towards the attitude object and reflect the individuals' conception of whether a certain attitude object is important or not. This happens to individuals depending on the knowledge they have towards behavior. In this context low knowledge on careers activities might be the reason for negative to undecided level of attitude for many government school students as opposed to students in international schools..

Franzoi (2000) add that, the existence of an attitude is inferred from a certain class of evaluation responses to the attitude object. That is to say the common characteristics of attitude is its evaluative nature which is such as dislike, love or hate, and pleasant or unpleasant. All these facts confirm that, the positive attitude expressed by international school students indicates their like and positive consideration of career services provided in their schools as opposed to government school students who are not sure of the usefulness of this service in their schools. Furthermore, it is argued that people

who evaluate an attitude object favorably tend to engage in behaviors that foster or support it and people who evaluate an attitude object unfavorably tend to engage in behaviors that hinder or oppose it (Libent, 2003). Arguing in the same line Ajzen (1999) emphasized that; the more positive the general image on career services the greater the probability for participating in that particular activity.

Considering the observed facts and the arguments from various scholars, the researcher wish to make a recommendation that, there is still a lot of work to do in making career services delivery a reality in our schools. This is because; with this trend of attitude students in government

schools are more likely to keep less commitment and little enrngy in career activities in schools. Such situation can compromise with student's ability to link their personal attributes and their career of interest at the end of the day many of them be in problems in course choices in colleges and universities and which have impact also in job decision making. Therefore, the facts in this paper calls for improvement in the provision of career services delivery among government school students so as to change their attitudes towards these services and enable them to benefit from the few career activities offere in schools so as to enable these students to make informed career decision at the end of their school journey.

Career Knowledge for Students in Government and International Schools

Using descriptive statistics, career knowledge between students in international and government school was assessed and the results are as indicated in Table 2.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics for Career Knowledge among School Students

Type of school	N	Mean	SD	t	Df	Sig. level
Government	183	28.88	6.76	-11.03	193.84	.000
International	132	41.37	11.67			

Mean difference is significant at $p < .05$

Field data indicate a large variation in mean scores for students' knowledge in different careers. The t-test shows that there was a significant difference in scores for government school students ($M = 28.88$, $SD = 6.76$) and international school students [$M = 41.37$, $SD = 11.67$; $t(194) = -11.03$, $p = .000$]. The magnitude of the differences in the mean scores between the two categories of schools studied was large at eta squared = .279, which is 27.9 percent. The observed difference in career knowledge can be linked to the few and weak career programmes conducted by untrained career teachers in government schools (Nkuba, 2010). In line to this observation, Biswalo (1996) explains that, the career services provision in many secondary schools in Tanzania is still less effective due to lack of trained career counselors, career instructional materials and career facilities a factor which limits the knowledge of students on careers.

Moreover the significant difference in the level of career knowledge between students in international and government schools can be linked to the poor implementation of the government notes number 11: 2002 which emphasized the need for counseling services in schools in Tanzania (URT, 2002). Furthermore, the guideline for secondary school heads in Tanzania explain how well career services should be conducted in the country to help students in government schools in making career decision a reality. It emphasize that, every school in Tanzania should have career masters or career mistress who will be responsible in guiding students about career choice and supervising different career services (MOEC, 1997).

During focus group discussion, one student from one of the international schools included in the study explained that; *"Our career counselo normally gives us different career documents which help us in career decision making. We always meet once every week for discussion on how to match our personal attributes and careers of our interest. We get from the discussion a lot of information about careers and criteria's for university selection and how to obtain scholarships both in local and international universities"*.

Contributing in the same aspect during focus group discussion, one student from one of the government schools, explained that;

Majority of us we don't know which courses are available in universities related with our current subject combinations. ...off course we have interest in some areas of work, example myself I like to do commerce but I don't know how to reach there and which are good courses available at the university in order to end in the career of my dream".

Generally, the situation in government schools appear to be different from what Parson in the Trait and Factor theory emphasizes. He emphasize that, to select a career an individual should ideally have; first information which indicates a clear understanding of himself or herself, his or her attitudes, abilities, ambitions, resources, limitations, and their causes. Second an individual should have the knowledge of the requirements and conditions of success, advantages and disadvantages, compensation, opportunities and prospects in different lines of work. Also an individual should have a true reasoning on relations of himself or herself and the requirements of success (Parson, 1909 as cited in Sharf 1992).

Hence more efforts are required so as to make career services provision a reality in Tanzania especially in government schools. This is possible by providing knowledge to students on courses which are available in our universities and other

universities out of our country and careers available in the world of work so as to help them in matching the available careers with their personal attributes.

Frequency of Students who Perceive Themselves Knowledgeable with Various Career Options as the Result of Career Activities Available in Schools

Table5: Frequency of students in Different Types of Careers

Careers Identified	Response from Government and International School Students	
	Government students (190)	International students (132)
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Accountant	94 (49.5)	90 (68.1)
Engineer	62. (32.6)	70 (53)
Translator	57 (30.1)	65 (49.2)
Banker	47 (24.9)	85 (64.4)
Journalist	50 (26.4)	80 (60.6)
Teacher	183 (96.3)	131 (99.2)
Pilot	52 (27.4)	75 (56.7)
Driver	58 (30.6)	79 (59.9)
Geologist	48 (25.4)	65 (49.3)
Farmer	54 (28.5)	89 (67.4)
Priest	50 (26.3)	72 (54.5)
Pharmacist	55 (29)	73 (55.3)
Army	64 (33.8)	70(53)
Nurse	65 (34.4)	85(64.4)

In order of familiarity the researcher was interested to hear from students on whether are they comfortably aware with some careers and if they know what is needed to attain qualifications and get working in those careers. It is true to the fact that very few were able to explain correctly in the requirements of various careers. In fact teaching was identified correctly by 275 respondents (85.4%) individuals out of the total sampled students and this can be attributed to the fact teachers are the only individuals who are mostly interacting with these students, followed by Accounting 184 respondents (57.1%), Nursing 145 respondents (45.2%), Army 144 respondents (44.7%), Farmer 143 respondents (44.4%), Driving 137 respondents (42.7%), Banking 132 respondents (41.1%) and Engineering 132 respondents (41.1%). High understanding of students of these occupations can also attributed by social factors and the context, since all of these respondents are in Dar es salaam where most of these occupations are revealed easily. However, many students showed extremely low knowledge in several career options such as Geologist 113 respondents (35.2%), Priest 122 respondents (37.9%), Pilot 127 respondents (39.7%), Pharmacist 127 respondents (39.8%), and Journalist 128 respondents (39.7%).

The low knowledge among students in explaining the roles of professionals such as geologists, pilots, priests, nurses, engineers, army personnel and pharmacist can be attributed to

less exposure of students in career programmes which act as source of career information. The lack of trained career counselors in many schools is another factor seen to the source of this dilemma during data correction. This reflects the inadequate implementation of the Tanzania Education Policy which specifies that, teachers should prepare students to fit in the world of work by linking their school learning and job market while considering their academic abilities, interests and job market (MOEC, 1995). Similarly, the guideline provided by the government to school heads in order to guide the process of career services provision seems to be not yet to be kept in implementation. This is because there is no evidence of implementing the objectives stated in this document which emphasize on the need for school career counselors to help students in subject and career decision making (MOEC, 1997). The situation is happening this way because the appointed teachers to do the role of career counseling are not trained in career counseling, no facilities and guiding documents. Hence this task seems to be abstract and difficult to these untrained career counselors the situation which course career counseling in our schools remain unrealistic and a mere dream.

During focus group discussion, one student from one of the government schools reported that, he received advice from parents and relatives to take courses related to accounting so

as to be in a position of getting careers with good pay, he emphasized that;

“It is a respect today to study courses which are related to money, this is because, we are studying for the purpose of getting return in terms of money and the issue of services follows. That is why we are interested to know how we can reach in careers which are related to good pay”.

The argument from students gives the picture that, students in schools struggle to get information on careers of their interests and which are viewed as good by many people in the society. This situation attracts students to a few careers which are common to many members of the society leaving out other careers, a situation which limits their career choice. In support of this argument Cobb (2001) and Santrock (2005) emphasize that from an early age of development children see and hear about the job done by those people who are successful and important to them. At this point they try to know the requirements and how they can reach those careers so as to relate with their role models.

In addition to this argument, Mugonzibwa, Kikwilu, Rugarabamu and Ntabaye (2000) conducted a study on factors influencing choice of medical careers among high school students in Tanzania. In this study students specified that, image of the profession in terms of attractiveness and command of high respect in the society is the most considered factors in career decision making. Similarly, Hezron (2008) in the study about psychosocial determinant for career choice among young people in the Kuria community in Tanzania found that, the predictive power of significant others in career choice was strong at $r = .59, p < .01$. Generally, the overall low career knowledge in various career options gives the signal that, students are more likely to engage in careers which do not match with their personal attributes, a factor which might lead to low job satisfaction, frustration and high occupation turn over the situation which happening today in the teaching profession in Tanzania.

However, in comparing the results in government and international school students, results indicate that, many students in international schools have good knowledge on many career options than government school students. This was evident as seen in teaching 131 respondents (99.2%), accounting 90 respondent (68.1%), farming 89 respondent (67.4%) and banking 85 respondent (64.4%) as compared to 183 respondents (96.3%) in teaching, 94 respondent (49.5%) in accounting, 54 respondents (28.5%) in farming and 47 respondents (24.9%) in banking from government school students. The differences suggest that, there is variation in knowledge provision to students between government and international schools. In support of this fact Kidd (20006) argues that, “when provided at the right moment, the knowledge of various careers can help an individual to make a big difference in career planning. This calls for improving the provision of career services delivery in government schools so as to relate or improve in line with the services offered in international schools.

Teacher Counselors’ Comments on Career Services in their Schools

To answer this question, six career counselors were interviewed; three from government schools and other three from international schools. From the government school career counselors the researcher observed that, teachers who were appointed to conduct career counseling and other related career programmes were implementing this service without knowing exactly their responsibilities. Some of the teacher counselors said that;

“What I know is that career services were introduced for the purpose of helping students on deciding subject streams and subject combination. Although I have a diploma in education but in reality I don’t know what exactly I have to do with career services provision, no any training or guideline I was given especially on how to conduct the service. This made my activity difficult, the situation which resulted into less effective career service provision at my school” [Career mistress from one of government schools said].

“The main objective of career services in our school is difficult to specify, but I always advise students in subject combination choice and job choice. I was appointed to this post by the head of my school without any training and there is no syllabus or manual on how to conduct the service. At my university studies where I did Bachelor of Arts with education, I was not exposed to career counseling courses. It is good to improve it” [Said the career master from another selected government school].

“The main objective of career service is counseling students in different social problems ranging from academic to health problems. I always discuss with students and help them depending on the nature of the problem. No training I received or syllabus for my tasks. In my bachelor degree at the university, career counseling courses were not taught” [Career mistress from another selected government secondary school specified].

When the same question asked by the researcher to international school teachers, the following responses were provided;

“The aim of career services at our school is to orient students to different study opportunities in higher institutions. Apart from that, the service focus at exposing students to job opportunities available after their school life. This is possible through giving students the necessary information in matching their school studies and job choice.” [Careers counselor from one of the selected international schools commented].

“Career services are offered at our school for the purpose of providing knowledge and skills on how to link school studies and the job market. At our school the service helped many students to reduce the try and error style in subject

combination choice” [Careers counselor at another selected international school pointed out].

“Career services at our school aims at helping students in linking students with areas of work available in the world of work. It focuses on helping students to select subject of studies according to their academic ability, personal interest, study opportunities in higher institutions and type of job they aspire after school” [Career counselor from another International School insisted].

From the interview between government school teachers and international school teachers, it can be concluded that, the understanding of teachers in international schools towards career services provision in Tanzania reflect good career knowledge the factor which have contribution to students orientation.

The situation is different among government school teachers as they seem to be not understanding of what career counseling intends and the way of implementing. Drawing from the discussion with teachers it is evident that in government schools teachers have been given the task of counseling students without enough training and guideline as opposed to the situation which was observed in international secondary schools during the interview with school career counselors. Hence it is the researchers’ opinion that the government in collaboration with higher learning institutions and education colleges should see the need for placing in schools trained career counselors so as to help our children in making appropriate subject choices and finally to end in meaningful career choices in line to their personal attributes.

Head of Schools’ Perception towards Career Services Delivery in their Schools

The study was also interested in assessing the perception of school heads about career services in their schools. The main focus was to know the criteria used in appointing career counselors, training for career counselors and ways used to evaluate career services in schools. Responding to these questions, heads from government schools explained;

“We appoint career counselors to respond to the Ministry’s instruction which require heads of schools to appoint one teacher who can help students in subject and job choice. We believe that, our teachers have this knowledge from colleges and universities. The career mistress can explain more on the success of the service” [Head of school from one of the studied government schools explained].

“I appointed the career master in response to instruction from the ministry of education. The expectation is that, my teachers learned about counseling in their university studies. We are not yet to evaluate the service” [Head of school from another selected government school said].

“As head of school I’m required by the ministry of education to appoint one of my teachers for the purpose of advising

students about subject and job choice. The school has not conducted any career training for our teachers but I believe they use their experience from colleges on how to organise the service and help students.” [Head of school from selected government school explained].

Addressing the same question, the heads of schools from the selected international schools revealed that;

“Our careers counseling office have professionally trained career counselor, who is trained in educational counseling and educational psychology. The teacher is responsible in organizing all career activities for students at school. We are doing well” [Head of school from selected international secondary school said].

“We have a counselor who is professionally trained. Furthermore our teachers attend workshops organized by Cambridge University focusing on career counseling skills. The service is good and helpful for our students” [Head of school from another international secondary school said].

We have one career counselor; we also train some of our teachers in short counseling courses for this purpose. Cambridge University sometimes helps us in provision of training and career workshops for our students. It is good service and has helped our students very much in career decision making” [Head of school from another international secondary school said].

Considering the views provided by the school heads, it is evident that, there is low commitment in career services delivery in government schools as compared to heads of schools in international schools. This was reflected in their failure to explain the status of career services offered in their schools and by appointing teachers to conduct career services without any training, guideline as well as facilities. This is also means that, there is failure in implementing the guideline to heads of schools provided to all schools which emphasize the role of the school heads in making career services effective in schools. One of the guidelines in this document specify that; “The head of school should appoint career master/mistress who will evaluate students ability and encourage them to continue with higher studies, vocational education in different specializations and advise other students who will not make to this levels to join directly in various occupations depending with their personal attributes and competences” (MOEC, 1997 page 20 sect. 1e.). In line to this observation the researcher is emphasizing the need for heads of schools to play their part and report any challenges to the ministry or collaborate with other non-governmental agencies so as to make career services delivery a reality in schools.

Issues and Implications for Career Services Delivery in Tanzania Schools

- Low career knowledge among students in schools is a problem to our students and outgoing school leavers. Such situation can be the best explanation for the current unemployment in our country and high rate of workers moving from one occupation to another which is a current practice for some occupations such as teaching in our country..
- Students low participation in career services in schools which might be linked to low attitude towards career activities conducted in school. This might be the result of no or less efforts used to educate students on the need for attending to services available in schools..This fact call for need for seminar and workshops with an intention of increasing awareness on the available career services.
- Presence of untrained career counselors, heads of schools with low commitment, challenge due to lack of facilities need the government to re-think and make sure that the good instruction sent to schools are kept in practice

Conclusions

This paper has established new understanding on the role of students, teacher counselors and heads of schools towards career services delivery to secondary schools in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. From the findings it can be concluded that, students' attitudes and teachers' perception have influence on career services delivery in Tanzania schools. This is because at the point where the attitudes were negative especially in government schools, the provision of career services revealed to be ineffective and vice-versa is true as evidenced in international schools. It was interesting that, teachers in government schools acknowledged the inadequate and ineffective career services provision to students and argued that it was not their task rather the ministry's task to rectify the situation as opposed to international school teachers. Therefore, these findings are unique to Dar es Salaam, Tanzania and call for government, education stakeholders and schools to improve career services delivery by using experience from international schools which are relatively doing well in career services delivery.

Recommendations

Government and educational institutions should work together so as to train school career counselors and provide career instructional materials so that career services delivery can be effective in Tanzania schools. Furthermore government schools should establish properly coordinated career education services in collaboration with international schools. This can be properly coordinated through established department at the ministry. The findings of this study might have largely reflected career services provision to high school students in Dar es salaam, since this study was based on cross sectional survey. Therefore, a longitudinal study ranging from primary schools to colleges would be essential so as to show in detail the causes and effects of inadequate career services provision in education institutions in the country. Finally, the inadequate

career guidance and counseling training among teacher trainees and its implication on career services delivery in schools can also be researched.

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